

Material Suplementario

Tabla S1. Set de datos de Chondrolia Chalkidikis y Koroneiki.

Muestra (ID)	Variedad	Código de secuencia (NCBI)
chondrolia_endocarp_stage2_3	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901550
chondrolia_endocarp_stage2_2	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901551
chondrolia_endocarp_stage2_1	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901552
chondrolia_endocarp_stage3_3	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901543
chondrolia_endocarp_stage3_2	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901544
chondrolia_endocarp_stage3_1	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901545
chondrolia_endocarp_stage4_3	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901537
chondrolia_endocarp_stage4_2	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901538
chondrolia_endocarp_stage4_1	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901539
chondrolia_fruits_stage2_3	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901553
chondrolia_fruits_stage2_2	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901554
chondrolia_fruits_stage2_1	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901555
chondrolia_fruits_stage3_3	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901547
chondrolia_fruits_stage3_2	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901548
chondrolia_fruits_stage3_1	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901549
chondrolia_fruits_stage4_3	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901540
chondrolia_fruits_stage4_2	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901541

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chondrolia_fruits_stage4_1	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901542
chondrolia_roots_3	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901556
chondrolia_roots_2	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901558
chondrolia_roots_1	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901559
chondrolia_flowers_open_3	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901560
chondrolia_flowers_open_2	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901561
chondrolia_flowers_open_1	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901562
chondrolia_flowers_closed_3	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901563
chondrolia_flowers_closed_2	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901564
chondrolia_flowers_closed_1	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901565
chondrolia_leaves_young_3	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901557
chondrolia_leaves_young_2	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901568
chondrolia_leaves_young_1	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901569
chondrolia_leaves_mature_3	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901491
chondrolia_leaves_mature_2	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901502
chondrolia_leaves_mature_1	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901513
chondrolia_shoot_young_3	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901524
chondrolia_shoot_young_2	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901535
chondrolia_shoot_young_1	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901546

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chondrolia_shoot_mature_3	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901566
chondrolia_shoot_mature_2	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901567
chondrolia_shoot_mature_1	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901486
chondrolia_stalk_stage4_3	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901533
chondrolia_stalk_stage4_2	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901534
chondrolia_stalk_stage4_1	Chondrolia Chalkidikis	SRR15901536
koroneiki_endocarp_stage2_1	Koroneiki	SRR15901506
koroneiki_endocarp_stage2_2	Koroneiki	SRR15901505
koroneiki_endocarp_stage2_3	Koroneiki	SRR15901504
koroneiki_endocarp_stage3_1	Koroneiki	SRR15901499
koroneiki_endocarp_stage3_2	Koroneiki	SRR15901498
koroneiki_endocarp_stage3_3	Koroneiki	SRR15901497
koroneiki_endocarp_stage4_1	Koroneiki	SRR15901493
koroneiki_endocarp_stage4_2	Koroneiki	SRR15901492
koroneiki_endocarp_stage4_3	Koroneiki	SRR15901490
koroneiki_flowers_closed_1	Koroneiki	SRR15901519
koroneiki_flowers_closed_2	Koroneiki	SRR15901518
koroneiki_flowers_closed_3	Koroneiki	SRR15901517
koroneiki_flowers_open_1	Koroneiki	SRR15901516

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koroneiki_flowers_open_2	Koroneiki	SRR15901515
koroneiki_flowers_open_3	Koroneiki	SRR15901514
koroneiki_fruits_stage2_1	Koroneiki	SRR15901509
koroneiki_fruits_stage2_2	Koroneiki	SRR15901508
koroneiki_fruits_stage2_3	Koroneiki	SRR15901507
koroneiki_fruits_stage3_1	Koroneiki	SRR15901503
koroneiki_fruits_stage3_2	Koroneiki	SRR15901501
koroneiki_fruits_stage3_3	Koroneiki	SRR15901500
koroneiki_fruits_stage4_1	Koroneiki	SRR15901496
koroneiki_fruits_stage4_2	Koroneiki	SRR15901495
koroneiki_fruits_stage4_3	Koroneiki	SRR15901494
koroneiki_roots_1	Koroneiki	SRR15901512
koroneiki_roots_2	Koroneiki	SRR15901511
koroneiki_roots_3	Koroneiki	SRR15901510
koroneiki_shoot_mature_1	Koroneiki	SRR15901522
koroneiki_shoot_mature_2	Koroneiki	SRR15901521
koroneiki_shoot_mature_3	Koroneiki	SRR15901520
koroneiki_stalk_stage4_1	Koroneiki	SRR15901489
koroneiki_stalk_stage4_2	Koroneiki	SRR15901488

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koroneiki_stalk_stage4_3	Koroneiki	SRR15901487
koroneiki_leaves_mature_1	Koroneiki	SRR15901526
koroneiki_leaves_mature_2	Koroneiki	SRR15901525
koroneiki_leaves_mature_3	Koroneiki	SRR15901523
koroneiki_leaves_young_3	Koroneiki	SRR15901530
koroneiki_leaves_young_2	Koroneiki	SRR15901531
koroneiki_leaves_young_1	Koroneiki	SRR15901532
koroneiki_shoot_young_3	Koroneiki	SRR15901527
koroneiki_shoot_young_2	Koroneiki	SRR15901528
koroneiki_shoot_young_1	Koroneiki	SRR15901529

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Tabla S2. Porcentaje de lecturas útiles después de limpieza con Trimmomatic, Variedad Chondrolia Chalkidikis.

Muestras	Lecturas crudas	Lecturas limpias	Supervivencia
chondrolia_endocarp_stage2_1	12817640	12526429	98%
chondrolia_endocarp_stage2_2	13173786	12834429	97%
chondrolia_endocarp_stage2_3	12154640	11847022	97%
chondrolia_endocarp_stage3_1	13157322	12623799	96%
chondrolia_endocarp_stage3_2	12819453	12421341	97%
chondrolia_endocarp_stage3_3	12639130	12334567	98%
chondrolia_endocarp_stage4_1	12215893	11813724	97%
chondrolia_endocarp_stage4_2	10999847	10523961	96%
chondrolia_endocarp_stage4_3	16677018	16270395	98%
chondrolia_flowers_closed_1	12405316	11886147	96%
chondrolia_flowers_closed_2	12703636	11706998	92%
chondrolia_flowers_closed_3	17554068	16671396	95%
chondrolia_flowers_open_1	15262141	14779580	97%
chondrolia_flowers_open_2	11890454	11542238	97%
chondrolia_flowers_open_3	17411652	16833597	97%
chondrolia_fruits_stage2_1	13144981	12738416	97%
chondrolia_fruits_stage2_2	11899020	11601688	98%

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chondrolia_fruits_stage2_3	14169770	13745932	97%
chondrolia_fruits_stage3_1	13131020	12787174	97%
chondrolia_fruits_stage3_2	14361223	13843385	96%
chondrolia_fruits_stage3_3	16247925	15354945	95%
chondrolia_fruits_stage4_1	17947242	17533110	98%
chondrolia_fruits_stage4_2	14140959	13774901	97%
chondrolia_fruits_stage4_3	15211584	14660928	96%
chondrolia_roots_1	13088112	12767135	98%
chondrolia_roots_2	11008500	10552946	96%
chondrolia_roots_3	13167169	12388967	94%
chondrolia_stalk_stage4_1	11743487	11159846	95%
chondrolia_stalk_stage4_2	13435903	13015084	97%
chondrolia_stalk_stage4_3	15962210	14730562	92%
chondrolia_leaves_mature_1	13619036	12789116	94%
chondrolia_leaves_mature_2	13708584	13118925	96%
chondrolia_leaves_mature_3	18328747	17486582	95%
chondrolia_shoot_young_1	27456953	26289624	96%
chondrolia_shoot_young_2	11315938	10691109	94%
chondrolia_shoot_young_3	12640916	11496741	91%

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chondrolia_leaves_young_1	13684573	13020788	95%
chondrolia_leaves_young_2	12395321	11942374	96%
chondrolia_leaves_young_3	18709388	17457626	93%
chondrolia_shoot_mature_1	13548977	11993391	89%
chondrolia_shoot_mature_2	14226733	12472352	88%
chondrolia_shoot_mature_3	18398768	17598394	96%
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Muestras	Lecturas crudas	Lecturas limpias	Supervivencia
koroneiki_endocarp_stage2_1	20226801	15958139	78.9%
koroneiki_endocarp_stage2_2	18496619	14461075	78.2%
koroneiki_endocarp_stage2_3	21108532	16255941	77.0%
koroneiki_endocarp_stage3_1	20861182	16112535	77.2%
koroneiki_endocarp_stage3_2	21745650	17408355	80.1%
koroneiki_endocarp_stage3_3	22546944	16631279	73.8%
koroneiki_endocarp_stage4_1	19349407	11799515	61.0%
koroneiki_endocarp_stage4_2	20073221	12931991	64.4%
koroneiki_endocarp_stage4_3	27415261	17599044	64.2%
koroneiki_flowers_closed_1	22119669	16609637	75.1%
koroneiki_flowers_closed_2	21293574	15696631	73.7%

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koroneiki_flowers_closed_3	22582275	16337078	72.3%
koroneiki_flowers_open_1	20400244	14295513	70.1%
koroneiki_flowers_open_2	18554889	13608060	73.3%
koroneiki_flowers_open_3	19088206	14036225	73.5%
koroneiki_fruits_stage2_1	19904060	13521883	67.9%
koroneiki_fruits_stage2_2	22519330	16946420	75.3%
koroneiki_fruits_stage2_3	24244084	17992108	74.2%
koroneiki_fruits_stage3_1	22917077	17375988	75.8%
koroneiki_fruits_stage3_2	23768022	17331551	72.9%
koroneiki_fruits_stage3_3	22014630	17262919	78.4%
koroneiki_fruits_stage4_1	20955483	12255170	58.5%
koroneiki_fruits_stage4_2	19718577	12368650	62.7%
koroneiki_fruits_stage4_3	18206171	11482766	63.1%
koroneiki_roots_1	22362155	17284689	77.3%
koroneiki_roots_2	21011617	16207725	77.1%
koroneiki_roots_3	23871736	18399616	77.1%
koroneiki_stalk_stage4_1	19612305	12907319	65.8%
koroneiki_stalk_stage4_2	24569438	16007591	65.2%
koroneiki_stalk_stage4_3	19034467	12129647	63.7%

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koroneiki_leaves_mature_1	30850910	21205623	68.7%
koroneiki_leaves_mature_2	29002290	19861319	68.5%
koroneiki_leaves_mature_3	13832943	92468376	66.8%
koroneiki_leaves_young_1	32715012	24107221	73.7%
koroneiki_leaves_young_2	33930614	23597234	69.5%
koroneiki_leaves_young_3	34015555	22903453	67.3%
koroneiki_shoot_young_1	33539745	26214993	78.2%
koroneiki_shoot_young_2	35435286	27505274	77.6%
koroneiki_shoot_young_3	38630648	28013413	72.5%
koroneiki_shoot_mature_1	32819848	21777510	66.4%
koroneiki_shoot_mature_2	27001874	18531375	68.6%
koroneiki_shoot_mature_3	26561032	18119482	68.2%